

FRIABILITY, THERMAL STABILITY, AND EFFECT OF HYGROTHERMAL AGING ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF LIGNIN- AND WOOD-REINFORCED PHENOLIC FOAMS

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ABSTRACT

The determination of the friability and thermal stability of lignin nanoparticle- and wood flour-reinforced phenolic foams, as well as the knowledge of the behavior of these materials under moisture and temperature is essential to evaluate their suitability for structural and insulating applications. In the present work, the influence of two reinforcement, lignin nanoparticle and wood flour, on friability and thermal stability of a phenolic foam, as well as the effect of hygrothermal aging on compressive mechanical properties of lignin nanoparticle- and wood flour-reinforced phenolic foams were studied.

1 INTRODUCTION

Closed cell phenolic foams show excellent fire properties and high thermal stability in a wide range of temperature, which have led to use them as insulators in applications where fire resistance is critical such as in buildings [1]. However, phenolic foams are extremely friable and show relatively low mechanical performance in relation to other commercial polymeric foams [2, 3]. Thus, the use of these materials in some applications is limited and many efforts have been developed to strengthen them through the incorporation of several reinforcements [1, 4, 5].

In the last years, the use of reinforcements from natural resources in polymeric foams has attracted the attention of many researchers since these reinforcements show high biodegradability, renewability, and low density and cost [6, 7]. Another interesting advantage of using these bio-reinforcements is that usually the resulting material has a lower environmental impact than compared to conventional reinforcements are employed in the manufacturing of polymeric foams.

The determination of the friability and thermal stability of lignin nanoparticle- and wood flour-reinforced phenolic foams, as well as the knowledge of the behavior of these materials under moisture and temperature is essential to evaluate their suitability for structural and insulating applications. Materials with a high friability generate dust in the workplace causing a hazard for human health [2], and, in the case of polymeric foams, limit their applications in sandwich panels, where a good adhesion of the materials is required [8]. The thermal stability of polymeric materials is crucial to avoid their degradation, and is usually studied by thermogravimetric analysis. Aging tests are commonly performed to study the effect of moisture, temperature, light, etc. on the properties of polymeric materials, since these variables can have negative effects on some properties of the material such as mechanical properties [9].

In this work, the influence of lignin nanoparticle and wood flour reinforcements on friability and thermal stability of a phenolic foam was determined. Moreover, the effect of hygrothermal aging on compressive mechanical properties of the two reinforced materials were studied. This research allowed determining which was the reinforced phenolic foam with the best features for structural and insulating applications: the lowest friability, the highest thermal stability and the greatest mechanical properties after hygrothermal aging.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Preparation of the materials

Momentive Specialty Chemicals provided the phenolic resol resin and hardener (ACE 1035) employed to prepare the materials. Phenolic foams were synthesized using Tween® 40 (Sigma Aldrich), phenol-4-sulfonic acid (Sigma Aldrich), and n-pentane (Panreac), as surfactant, catalyst and blowing agent, respectively. Materials were prepared with a density of 120 kg.m⁻³ as was described in previous works [4, 5]. Lignin nanoparticle was calcium softwood lignosulfonate with an average diameter of 1.6 µm and was supplied by LignoTech Ibérica. Wood flour with a size < 0.15 mm was obtained after milling and sieving of industrial chips of *Pinus radiata* provided by Instituto Nacional de Investigación y Tecnología Agraria y Alimentaria (CIFOR-INIA).

The weight fractions of lignin nanoparticle and wood flour weight fractions incorporated as reinforcement to the phenolic foam for friability and thermal stability studies were 1.5, 5 and 8.5 wt.%. For the hygrothermal aging study, reinforcements weight fractions of lignin nanoparticle and wood flour incorporated in the material were 8.5 wt.% and 1.5 wt.%, respectively. These weight fractions were selected since they allow obtaining the greatest mechanical properties of the material, as was reported in previous works [4, 5].

2.2 Friability and hygrothermal aging tests

Friability tests were performed according to ASTM C421 for block-type thermal insulation. Samples of the lignin reinforced (LRPF), wood flour reinforced (WRPF) and reference (PF) phenolic foams were cut and polished to obtain cubic specimens of 25.4 mm of side. The specimens were weighted before and after the tests and friability was determined as the percent of mass loss as follows:

$$\text{Mass loss (\%)} = \frac{m_f - m_o}{m_o} \cdot 100 \quad (1)$$

where m_o is the initial mass and m_f is the final mass of the sample.

Hygrothermal aging was performed according to ASTM D2126 for rigid cellular plastics [19]. The samples were cut with a keyhole saw Bosch PST 900 PEL and polished with a Buehler MetaServ® 3000 to obtain specimens of 80x80x30 mm. Specimens were placed in a Vötsch VCL 4006 environmental chamber at 38 °C and 97 % of relative humidity for two weeks.

2.3 Thermogravimetric tests

Thermal stability of the foams was studied by thermogravimetric analysis using a Mettler-Toledo TGA/DSC1 TG apparatus. The size of the foam samples was 5 ± 0.5 mg, while in the case of the reinforcements, lignin nanoparticle and wood flour, was 10 ± 0.5 mg. Samples were placed in a 70 µL alumina pan and a heating program from 30 to 900 °C, using a heating rate of 10 °C.min⁻¹, was employed to study their thermal stabilities. The tests were performed under nitrogen atmosphere at a flow of 20 mL.min⁻¹. $T_{5\%}$ and $T_{25\%}$ were determined as the temperature at which the materials showed a 5 and 25 % of mass loss, respectively. A minimum of three replicates of each sample were tested.

2.4 Compression tests

Compression tests of unaged and aged samples were performed according to ASTM D1621 using a Zwick/Roell Z030 universal testing machine. The samples were cut and polished to obtain cubic specimens of 25.4 mm of side. Specimens were placed between stainless steel plates and a load was applied uniformly with a crosshead rate of 2.5 mm.min⁻¹ in order to obtain strain-stress curves. Compressive modulus (E) was determined from the slope of the lineal step of the strain-stress curve. Compressive strength (σ_c) was obtained as the maximum strength of the strain-stress curve for strain ≤ 10 %. A minimum of five replicates of each sample were tested.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Friability tests

The values of mass loss of the PF and LRPF and WRPF at several reinforcement weight fractions are shown in Fig. 1. Friability of the foams was ranged between 22.2 – 41.8 % of mass loss. Friability of the studied phenolic foams exhibited similar values to those reported by Orpin [10] and Gardziella et al. [11], 15-25 % and < 30 %, respectively, for phenolic foams.

Figure 1: Mass loss during friability test for unreinforced and reinforced phenolic foams.

Mass loss of the specimen of the LRPF foam with an 8.5 wt.% of reinforcement was 22.2 %; whereas, for the PF was 32.2 %. Therefore, when 8.5 wt.% of lignin nanoparticle was incorporated in the phenolic foam, friability of the material decreased up to 31 % in relation to PF. This trend was due to lignin exhibits agglutinating properties, increasing toughness of the material [12]. The higher wood flour weight fraction incorporated as reinforcement the greater mass loss of the material. The mass loss of the WRPF with a 8.5 wt.% of wood flour was 41.8 %; i.e. an increase of 30 % of its friability in relation to the PF. This effect can be explained by the defects that wood flour could cause in the material such as cracks [13], which can favor mass loss of the foam during friability test. The results obtained suggest that the most competitive reinforced phenolic foam with respect to friability was 8.5 wt.% LRPF.

3.2 Thermal stability

Thermograms for PF, LRPF and WRPF with several reinforcement weight fractions and for lignin nanoparticle and wood flour employed as reinforcements are shown in Fig.2.

Foams studied in the present work showed that T5% and T25% ranged from 195.0-205.5 °C and 347.9-367.7 °C, respectively. T5% values are in accordance with the range reported by Hu et al. [14] (initial degradation temperature of 200 °C). However, these author obtained T25% higher than 500 °C for phenolic foams, which involves a higher thermal stability at T > 200 °C. Furthermore, commercial phenolic foams for insulating applications commonly do not require thermal stability temperatures higher than 120 °C. Therefore, the values obtained for thermal parameters of the materials studied in this work suggested that these materials could be suitable for the considered application.

Figure 2: Thermograms for a) PF, LRPF (1.5, 5 and 8.5 wt.%) and lignin; b) PF, WRPF (1.5, 5 and 8.5 wt.%) and wood flour.

Regarding the influence of the reinforcements on thermal stability of the material, the addition of lignin nanoparticle reinforcement had no effect on $T_{5\%}$ for all the weight fractions tested, i.e. no change was observed for $T_{5\%}$ of LRPFs with respect to the PF used as reference. However, $T_{25\%}$ decreased as the amount of lignin was increased; for instance, $T_{25\%}$ of 8.5 wt.% LRPF was 351.9 °C and for PF was 367.7 °C. For WRPF, the higher wood flour weight fraction in the WRPF, the greater $T_{5\%}$ and the lower $T_{25\%}$ of the reinforced material was obtained: $T_{5\%}$ of 8.5 wt.% WRPF was 205.5 °C, and for PF was 198.2 °C; $T_{25\%}$ of 8.5 wt.% WRPF was 347.9 °C, a drop of 22.4 °C compared to the PF. Therefore, the results obtained suggest that the most competitive reinforced phenolic foam with respect to thermal stability was 8.5 wt.% WRPF.

The effect of the amount of lignin reinforcement on the thermal stability of the foams can be explained by the thermograms obtained for lignin nanoparticles and PF (Fig. 2); the thermal stabilities of reinforced phenolic foams were intermediate between those for the phenolic foam and the reinforcement. Lignin nanoparticles showed a $T_{5\%}$ and $T_{25\%}$ of 229.3 °C and 325.4 °C, respectively; whereas, the values for PF were 198.0 °C and 367.7 °C. The difference between the thermal stability of PF and lignin is more noticed in the range of temperature of 250-500 °C, where lignin degrades significantly faster than PF, which explains that the effect of lignin nanoparticle appreciated for $T_{25\%}$ and negligible change observed in $T_{5\%}$.

Wood flour started thermal degradation at higher temperatures than PF ($T_{5\%}$ for wood flour was 272.2 °C, and for PF was 198.0 °C), i.e. wood flour reinforcement is more stable than the matrix according to the obtained results. Therefore, the increment of the $T_{5\%}$ observed as the weight percentage of wood flour reinforcement was increased is explained by the higher thermal stability of the reinforcement. In the range of 250-500 °C, wood flour degraded much faster than PF. $T_{25\%}$ for wood flour was 322.8 °C; whereas for PF the value was 367.7 °C. Therefore, the incorporation of wood flour in the phenolic foam reduced $T_{25\%}$ of the material.

3.3 Hygrothermal aging: effect on compressive properties

Strain-stress curves of PF, 8.5 wt.% LRPF and 1.5 wt.% WRPF before and after hygrothermal aging were obtained, as indicated in the experimental procedure section. From these curves, compressive modulus and strength before and after hygrothermal aging as well as the changes in these properties for PF, 8.5 wt.% LRPF and 1.5 wt.% WRPF were obtained and shown in Fig 3.

Figure 3: Compressive mechanical properties for unreinforced and reinforced phenolic foams before and after hygrothermal aging: a) Modulus b) Strength.

Before hygrothermal aging all reinforced phenolic foams studied showed greater compressive properties than the unreinforced phenolic foam, as reported in previous works [4, 5]. Compressive modulus and strength of 8.5 wt.% LRPF increased 43 and 81 % in relation to the PF, respectively. For 1.5 wt.% WRPF, the increases of modulus and strength in relation to the unreinforced material were 49 and 27 %, respectively.

The reduction found in compressive mechanical properties of reinforced phenolic foams studied after hygrothermal aging were higher than unreinforced phenolic foam, i.e. hygrothermal aging affected more significantly the mechanical properties of reinforced materials. For instance, the change in compressive modulus in relation to the values for each foam before aging was 61 % for the PF; whereas, for 8.5 wt.% LRPF and 1.5 wt. % WRPF were 69 and 66 %, respectively. This fact was due to moisture absorbed by the reinforced materials interacts with the reinforcements, which exhibit hydrophilic nature, decreasing the interaction matrix-reinforcements [9]. Although the drop of mechanical properties of the reinforced materials after hygrothermal aging was more pronounced than in the case of the unreinforced phenolic foam, compressive modulus and strength of the reinforced materials remained greater than for PF.

The values of compressive modulus and strength for 8.5 wt.% LRPF were 5.72 and 0.388 MPa, while for PF were 4.95 and 0.256 MPa, respectively. Thus, compressive modulus and strength of 8.5 wt.% LRPF were 15 and 52 % superior to those for PF, respectively. In the case of 1.5 wt.% WRPF, compressive modulus and strength after aging were 6.51 and 0.302 MPa, 31 and 18 % higher than those for the PF, respectively. The greatest combination of compressive mechanical properties before and after hygrothermal aging was obtained when 8.5 wt.% of lignin nanoparticle was incorporated in the phenolic foams.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Friability of phenolic foam decreased with lignin nanoparticle incorporation due to its agglomerating properties; whereas, it increased when wood flour was incorporated. Thermal stability of phenolic foam was slightly influenced by the incorporation of both reinforcements. The effect of hygrothermal aging on compressive mechanical properties of the foams was more noticeable for 8.5 wt.% LRPF and 1.5 wt.% WRPF than for PF, due to the interaction between moisture absorbed by the materials and the reinforcements. In general, the use of phenolic foams reinforced either with lignin nanoparticle or wood flour is competitive with respect to strength, friability and thermal stability in relation to commercial phenolic foams. The material which considering all the studied properties showed the best features was the phenolic foam reinforced with an 8.5 wt.% of lignin nanoparticle.

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